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“FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF CARBAMAZEPINE NANOEMULSION FOR BRAIN TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY VIA INTRANASAL ROUTE”

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ABSTRACT

Intranasal drug administration is receiving increased attention as a delivery method for bypassing the blood–brain barrier and rapidly targeting therapeutics to the brain or CNS. The objective of the present study was to select carbamazepine nanoemulsion for nose-to-brain delivery. Carbamazepine nanoemulsion (NE) formulations were successfully prepared by the spontaneous emulsification method (titration method) using Capmul MCM as the oil, Tween-80 as surfactant, and PEG-600 as co-surfactant phase on the basis of solubility studies. The nanoemulsion formulation containing 7.35% oil, 66.18% Smix ratio (3:1 Tween-80:PEG-600 ratio), 26.47% (v/v) aqueous phase that displayed an optical transparency of $99.42 \pm 0.81\%$, globule size of 71.70 ± 3.06 nm, and polydispersity index of 0.256 ± 0.002 . The selected Carbamazepine nanoemulsion was characterized, and the *in-vitro* drug release and *in-vivo* nasal absorption of drug from the selected formulation were evaluated in rats. *In-vitro* and *ex vivo* permeation studies showed an initial burst of drug release at 60 min and Carbamazepine nanoemulsion shows drug release up to 5 h. *In vivo* pharmacokinetic studies in rats showed that Carbamazepine.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, systemic drug delivery through nasal route has received a lot of attention, because of its advantages including rapid absorption, avoidance of hepatic first-pass metabolism and the ability for preferential drug delivery to brain via the olfactory region. In comparison with oral administration, intranasal drug delivery may provide an improvement in bioavailability and rapid onset of action. Thus, it is expected that intranasal delivery of Carbamazepine (CBZ) may also achieve rapid onset of action and improved bioavailability by avoiding the first-pass effect in the liver and intestine. Nanoemulsions are emulsions with mean droplet diameters ranging from 50 to 1000 nm. The particles can exist as oil-in-water and water-in-oil forms where the core of the particle is either oil or water, respectively. Overall, the treatment with CBZ is effective and safe. However, approximately 30–40% of epileptic patients do not respond very well to the treatment and CBZ may cause some adverse effects. For example, acute CBZ toxicity at therapeutic doses affects central nervous system and gastrointestinal system, causing sedation, ataxia, dizziness, nausea, vomiting, constipation and diarrhea. Long-term treatment with CBZ may modify plasma lipids, changes the concentration of sex hormones, produces hyponatremia, increases appetite and causes weight-gain, reduces the number of white blood cells and induces several allergic reactions. Currently CBZ is available only in the form of oral dosage forms including tablets, capsules, suspensions etc. The major limitation with CBZ oral formulation is its slower and erratic absorption and thus a novel formulation of CBZ to overcome the stated limitation is mandatory. CBZ transnasal formulations are not available in market. Some researchers have worked on CBZ nasal formulations but thorough characterization with pharmacodynamic studies has not been reported by the researchers as per the authors' knowledge. CBZ aqueous solubility is very poor and enhancement is necessary for intranasal delivery of CBZ as nasal delivery cannot permit administration of large volumes of liquids. Nanoemulsion seems to be convincing approach for administration of CBZ. Nanoemulsion is defined as a thermodynamically stable and transient dispersion consisting of oil, surfactant, cosurfactant and aqueous phases.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

Carbamazepine was obtained gift sample of Macleods Pharma Ltd, Daman. Capmul MCM was purchased from Abitech Corporation Limited, USA. Olive oil, Castor oil, Soybeans oil, Oleic acid, Sesame oil Isopropyl Myristate as a oils was purchased from Loba Chem, Mumbai Tween-20 and 80, Span-20, Poloxamer-188 and 407, Propylene Glycol Polyethylene Glycol-200,400,600, Transcutol HP as a surfactant was purchased from Loba Chem, Mumbai Ethanol, Methanol, Acetone, Acetonitrile as a solvent was purchased from Molychem lab, Mumbai.

Method

Solubility Determination

Selection of oil, surfactant, Co-surfactant based on the solubility of CBZ in them high drug solubility oil, surfactant, co-surfactant selected for the preparation of nanoemulsion. Solubility of CBZ was determined in various oils, surfactant, and cosurfactants by adding drug in excess to different oils, surfactants, and cosurfactants separately and stirred for 24 h on mechanical shaker, after 24 h the samples is centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min and the drug in the supernatant discarded remaining portion proper diluted with methanol, was analyzed in U.V. spectrophotometer at suitable wavelength. Then drug solubility (mg/mL) was calculated by linearity method.

Spontaneous Emulsification (Design of Pseudoternary Phase Diagrams)

The pseudoternary phase diagrams containing oily phase, surfactant, cosurfactants, and water was developed by the spontaneous emulsification method (Titration method). The surfactant was blended with a mixture of cosurfactant in fixed weight ratios, and aliquots of each surfactant and cosurfactant mixture (Smix) were then mixed with oil at ambient temperature. For each phase diagram, the ratio of oil to the Smix was varied as 9:1, 8:2, 7:3, 6:4, 5:5, 4:6, 3:7, 2:8, and 1:9 (W/W). Water was added drop wise to each oil-Smix mixture under vigorous stirring. After equilibrium, the samples were visually checked and determined as being clear nanoemulsion and emulsion region. No heating is conducted during the preparation. Phase diagrams were prepared by using Triplot Version.3.1 software.

FT-IR spectral analysis

CBZ was confirmed by FT-IR spectroscopy spectrum using Shimadzu 8300 spectrometer and Hyper FT-IR software from Shimadzu, Japan. The drug sample was dispersed in the KBr (200-400 mg) using a mortar, triturating the material into fine powder, and compressing the powder bed into the holder using a compression gauge with 140 mps pressure. The pellet was placed in the light path and the spectrum was recorded. The characteristic peaks of the functional groups were interpreted and compared with FT-IR spectrum as given in pharmacopoeial requirements.

Drug - excipients compatibility study

Physical compatibility and chemical compatibility of the water-insoluble drug with oil, surfactants co-surfactants should be used in oil, surfactants and co-surfactants selection procedure. Physical compatibility may include phase separation and color change in the drug surfactant solution during course study. Chemical compatibility is primarily regarded as the chemical stability of the drug with oil, surfactants and co-surfactants. oil, surfactants co-surfactants was considered for further development only if it was physically and chemically compatible with drug. Following study consider for drug - excipients compatibility study.

Pseudoternary phase diagram construction

The existence of nanoemulsion regions were determined using pseudo-ternary phase diagrams. The mixture of oil and surfactant/co-surfactant at certain weight ratios were diluted with water in a drop wise manner. Distill water was used as an aqueous phase for the construction of phase diagrams. For construction of pseudo ternary phase diagrams, water titration method was used because this method is easy and scalable. In this study, nanoemulsions were prepared to find the area of particular component system.

Electrical conductivity

Type of nanoemulsion (O/W or W/O) and the stability of the nanoemulsion (Phase inversion on storage) can be determined by electrical conductivity (σ). Electrical conductivity of nanoemulsion was measured by using digital conductometry by placing a conductivity electrode in the nanoemulsion formulation which calibrated by using NaCl solution. If nanoemulsion formulation show conductivity that indicate given nanoemulsion formulation was O/W type nanoemulsion.

Refractive index

Refractive index (RI) being an optical property is used to characterize the isotropic nature of the nanoemulsion. Refractive index of formulations was determined using an Abbe type refractometer and it was observed that the nanoemulsion formulations were chemically stable and remained isotropic in nature, thus having no drug excipient interaction.

pH

The pH nanoemulsion was measured using a tanco digital pH meter at 25 ± 1 °C. The pH meter was calibrated before use and pH value of all formulations were determined in triplicate.

Globule size or droplet size analysis

The globule size of all the formulations was analyzed by digital electronic microscope.

Percent drug Content

About 1 mL of nanoemulsion was taken and diluted appropriately with water up to 10mL and the drug content of the samples were estimated by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 280 nm.

Viscosity determination

The viscosity of the prepared nanoemulsion formulations were determined as such without dilution by Brookfield DV-I Rheometer (Brookfield Engineering Laboratories, Inc, Middleboro, MA). Viscosity of nanoemulsion determine by nanoemulsion formulation directly place under viscometer spindle which rotate at 10 RPM for 10 min

Ex-vivo diffusion study of nanoemulsion formulation

The freshly excised sheep nasal mucosa except the septum part was collected from the slaughter house in phosphate buffer, pH 6.4. The membrane was kept in PBS (pH 6.4) for 15 min to equilibrate. The superior nasal conche was identified and separated from the nasal membrane; the excised superior nasal membrane was mounted on Franz diffusion cell. The tissue was stabilized using phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) in both the compartments and allowed to stir for 15 min on a magnetic stirrer. After 15 min, solution from both the compartments was removed and fresh phosphate buffer (pH. 6.4) was filled in the acceptor compartment. The mounting of the nasal membrane was done using glue at the brim of the donor to avoid leakage of the test sample and supported with thread crossing over the cell. Franz diffusion cell used for *ex-vivo* diffusion studies had a diameter of 4.2cm. The temperature of the receiver chamber containing 15 mL of diffusion media (Phosphate buffer, pH 6.4) was controlled at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 1$ under continuous stirring with teflon-coated magnetic bar at a constant rate, in a way that the nasal membrane surface just flushes the diffusion fluid. A volume of 10 mL of each selected formulation was placed in the donor compartment of Franz diffusion cell along with 1.7 mL of phosphate buffer pH 6.4 added additionally. Samples from the receptor compartment were with drawn at predetermined time intervals and analyzed. Each sample removed was replaced by an equal volume of diffusion media. Each study was carried for a period of 6.0 h, during which the drug in receiver chamber ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) across the sheep nasal membrane was calculated at each sampling point. The formulations were studied in triplicate for diffusion studies and the mean cumulative values for % drug diffused versus time were plotted against time.

Droplet size analysis (Particle size distribution)

Droplet size of the prepared nanoemulsion was determined by using photon correlation spectroscopy, which analyzes the fluctuations in light scattering due to Brownian movement of the particles. The formulation (0.1 mL) was dispersed in 10 mL water (100 dilution) of highly pure double distilled water in a volumetric flask and gently mixed by inverting the flask. Particle size measurement was done by using a Delsa zeta nanosizer (Delsa Nano, UK). Light scattering was monitored at 25°C at a 90° angle and droplet size is Analyze.

Polydispersity Index

Polydispersity index of nanoemulsion was measured by using delasa nano instrument. Polydispersity is the ratio of standard deviation to the mean droplet size and denotes the uniformity of droplet size within the formulation. The lower the polydispersity value, higher is the uniformity of the droplet size in the formulation.

Zeta potential

Zeta-potential of the nanoemulsion were determined using Delsa nano zetasizer using clear disposable zeta cell. The principle was based on the particle diffusion due to Brownian motion, which is related to particle size. Particle size is then calculated from the translational diffusion coefficient using the Stokes-Einstein equation by in-built software. The electrophoretic mobility ($\mu\text{m/s}$) was converted to zeta potential by in-built software using Helmholtz- Smoluchowski equation. Measurements were performed using small volume disposable zeta cell. Average of three measurements of each sample was used to derive average zeta potential. Latex dispersion having zeta potential $-50 \text{ mV} \pm 2.5 \text{ mV}$ was used as a standard.

Transmission electron microscopy (Surface morphology)

The morphology of the nanoemulsion formulation NS1 was examined by Transmission electron microscopy (TEM-JEM-100SX, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan) study. One drop of diluted samples (1 mL nanoemulsion in 9 mL distilled water) was negatively stained by 2% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) and placed on film-coated copper grids followed by drying at 25°C before examination under the TEM.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

FT-IR spectra of CBZ

Figure No.1 FT-IR spectra of CBZ.

The principle absorption peak of drug in figure no.1 showed CONH_2 str at 3350 and 3370 cm^{-1} , CONH_2 bending at 1615 cm^{-1} , C-N str at 1100 cm^{-1} , Aromatic C-H str at 3050 cm^{-1} , C=O amide str at 1645 cm^{-1} , Aromatic C=C Str at 1450 cm^{-1} , O-Disubstituted Aromatic ring at 765 cm^{-1} . From this we could identified and authenticate that the given drug was CBZ.

FORMULATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF NANOEMULSION

Selection of excipients for nanoemulsion formulation

Figure No.2 Drug solubility determination in the various oils, surfactants and co-surfactants.

Result of solubility study of CBZ in different oils, surfactants and co-surfactant given in Table No From the results of solubility study of CBZ in different oils, surfactants and co-surfactant, it was found that CBZ was more soluble in Capmul MCM EP, Tween 80, and PEG 600 than other vehicles. Hence Capmul MCM EP was selected as oil, Tween 80 selected as surfactant, and PEG 600 co-surfactant.

Drug - excipients compatibility study

Appearance study

Appearances study and drug and excipient mixer does not show of any colour change of mixer that indicate drug and excipient mixer was chemically stable.

FT-IR Drug - excipients compatibility study

Figure No.3 FT-IR Interpretation of drug+excipient mixture.

From FT-IR studies revealed that there was no appearance of new peaks and disappearance of existing peaks, which indicated that there is no interaction between the CBZ and excipient mixture.

Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagrams

Surfactant and co-surfactant (Smix) in each group were mixed in different volume ratios (1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 1:2, 1:3,) and the stock of 100 mL of each group was prepared (Table No.8.24). These Smix ratios were chosen in increasing concentration of surfactant with respect to Co-surfactant and decreasing concentration of surfactant with respect to co-surfactant for detailed study of the phase diagrams for the nanoemulsion formation. In this method, surfactant was blended with co-surfactant in fixed weight ratios i.e. 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 2:1 and 3:1 for CBZ nanoemulsion. Aliquots of each surfactant and co-surfactant mixture (Smix) were then mixed with oil at ambient temperature. For each phase diagram, the ratio of oil to the Smix was varied as 9:1, 8:2, 7:3, 6:4, 5:5, 4:6, 3:7, 2:8, 1:9 (% v/v). Water was added drop wise to each oil-Smix mixture under vigorous stirring. After equilibrium, the samples were visually checked and determined as being clear nanoemulsion or emulsion or gel.

Figure No.4 Pseudo ternary phase diagram of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:1, 3:1 Smix ratio.

A ternary phase diagram explains the selection of the formulations from the phase diagrams to avoid metastable formulations having minimum surfactant concentration, in the least possible time. Ternary phase diagrams were constructed by varying Tween 80:PEG-600 ratios as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:1 and 3:1 (Figure No.4). The shaded areas of phase diagrams show the nanoemulsion regions, whereas the nonshaded area displays the emulsion region. Thus, the ternary phase system of Tween 80: PEG-600, (3:1) that exhibited maximum area for nanoemulsion formation was selected for the optimization of nanoemulsion batches. Apart from the ternary phase diagrams, globule size determinations were also performed as it could provide supportive evidence for the selection of phase diagram of ratio 3:1. It was clearly evident that an increase in the concentration of Tween 80 resulted in a decrease in globule size but 1:2 and 1:3 ration of Tween 80: PEG-600 does not show the long time stability so these rejected.

Characterization of CBZ nanoemulsion

Appearance Study

Nanoemulsion was checked for transparency to turbidity. Nanoemulsion remained clear and transparent, slightly yellowish easily flowable liquid formulation. Slightly yellow color of formulation appeared due to presence of synthetic oils and polysorbate derivatives as surfactants. Above parameter indicate that formulated nanoemulsion was clear transparent, slightly yellowish easily flowable liquid Formulation as such as main characteristics of nanoemulsion

Thermodynamic stability studies

Nanoemulsions are thermodynamically stable systems and are formed at a particular concentration of oil, surfactant, co-surfactant and distilled water, with no phase separation, creaming or cracking. Thermodynamically stable of nanoemulsion which differentiates it's from emulsions that have kinetic stability and will eventually phase separate. Thus, all selected formulations were subjected to different thermodynamic stability by using heating cooling cycle, centrifugation and freeze thaw cycle stress tests.

Percentage transmittance

Nanoemulsion was clear transparent liquid formulation containing oil as small droplet phase and water is continuous phase over the oil phase. The clarity of nanoemulsion was checked by transparency, measured in terms of transmittance (%T). In case of systems having %T values less than 95% suggest less clarity of nanoemulsion. This may be due to greater droplet size of the formulation, due to higher droplet size, oil globules might have reduced the transparency of nanoemulsion and thereby values of % T. The observed transparency of the system is due to the fact that the maximum size of the droplets of dispersed phase is not larger than $1/4^{\text{th}}$ of the wavelength of visible light. Thus, nanoemulsions scattered little light and therefore transparent or translucent.

Conductivity study

Type of nanoemulsion (O/W or W/O) and the stability of the nanoemulsion (Phase inversion on storage) can be determined by electrical conductivity (σ). If nanoemulsion formulation show conductivity that indicate given nanoemulsion formulation was o/w type nanoemulsion because in these type of emulsion, oil was small oil droplet phase and water was continuous phase that reason electrical conduction pass through the continuous phase but nanoemulsion formulation does not show conductivity that indicate the given nanoemulsion is W/O type nanoemulsion because in these type of emulsion water was small oil droplet phase and oil was continuous phase that reason electrical conduction does not pass through the continuous phase. The lowest electrical conductivity was found for 1:9 ratios of all smix ratio and the highest electrical conductivity was found for 5:5 and 4:6 ratio of 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 1:2, 1:3 of smix ratio respectively. This indicated that the formulation was o/w type. Electrical conductivity is directly proportional to the percentage of water. Higher the electrical conductivity more will be the percentage of water, which allows more freedom for mobility of ions.

Refractive index

Refractive index (RI) being an optical property is used to characterize the isotropic nature of the nanoemulsion. The RI of the selected formulations was determined using an Abe's type refractometer. Refractive index suppose of might have be in the range of 1.353-1.409 that indicate RI values increased with increase in concentration of oil and corresponding decrease in aqueous content. It was observed from the above table value of selected nanoemulsion formulations were chemically stable and remained isotropic in nature, thus having no drug excipient interactions.

pH

pH of selected formulation was found to be in the range of 4.92-5.45. All excipient use in the formulation which is slightly acidic in nature so these show the pH in the acidic region. pH of all the selected formulation in the range of 4.92-5.45 approximating the normal pH range of nasal fluids, which is one of the formulation consideration that may help reducing nasal toxicity of the formulation produced upon instillation. Hence all formulation pH nearby nasal fluid pH.

Globule size

It was observed that the particle size of all the formulations ranges between 166- 437 nm. The surfactant conc. had the effect on globule size. As the surfactant conc. increases globule size decreases.

Percent drug content

Percent drug content study of selected formulation was found to be in the range of 36-99, which indicate that nanoemulsion have more drug loading efficiency and less chance of drug lost in during formulation. During the spontaneous emulsification process, the surfactant molecules adsorb onto the newly formed oil-water interface, reducing the surface tension, facilitating the droplet disruption, and restricting the coalescence and aggregation of emulsion droplets. The adsorption kinetics of the emulsifier has a significant effect on the size and size distribution of the droplets. Consequently, the type and concentration of surfactant play a vital role in this process by influencing the adsorption kinetics and dynamic interfacial tension.

Viscosity

It was observed that the viscosities of all the formulations ranges between 64-186 centi poise. The viscosity plays an important role in nasal formulations. As the viscosity of formulation increases the retention time of drug also increases which gives effect for long time. From the viscosity data of CBZ nanoemulsion we could say that, the formulations had good viscosity which gives better flow properties across nasal cavity.

Ex- vivo diffusion study

The diffusion is faster due to presence of Capmul MCM, Tween 80 and PEG 600 which act as permeation enhancers. A biphasic release profile was obtained in which initial faster release was due to solubilized drug in continuous phase while slower rate was due to CBZ release from the oil droplets.

Study effect of changing of oil Smix ratio on the phase diagrams of the selected systems

Table No.1 effect of changing of oil Smix ratio on the 3:1 smix ratio phase diagrams of systems.

Sr.No.	Batch code	Ratio (O:S)*	Volume of different components in formulation				Percentage v/v of different components in formulation		
			Drug (mg/mL)	Oil (mL)	Smix (mL)	Water (mL)	Oil %	Smix %	Water %
1	NS1	1:9	10	0.25	2.25	0.9	7.35	66.18	26.47
2	NSE1	1:8	10	0.25	2	1.6	6.49	51.96	41.55
3	NSE2	1:7	10	0.25	1.75	2.1	6.09	42.68	51.21
4	NSE3	2:9	10	0.5	2.25	1.2	12.65	56.98	30.37
5	NS2	2:8	10	0.5	2	1.3	13.15	52.64	34.21
6	NSE4	2:7	10	0.5	1.75	1.9	12.04	42.16	45.78
7	NSE5	3:9	10	0.75	2.25	1.8	15.62	46.87	37.51
8	NSE6	3:8	10	0.75	2	2.1	15.46	41.25	43.29
9	NS3	3:7	10	0.75	1.75	1.8	17.44	40.69	41.87
10	NS4	4:6	10	1	1.50	2.5	20	30	50
11	NS5	5:5	10	1.25	1.25	3	22.72	22.72	54.56

*O:S:-oil:smix ratio (Smix ratio:-surfactant:co-surfactant)

Figure No.5 Pseudo ternary phase diagram of oil smix changing ratio.

In above phase diagram Figure No.5 clearly indicate the effect of changing of oil Smix ratio on phase diagram. If oil concentration increase with decrease the Smix concentration (surfactant:co-surfactant) they might have be increase chance of unstable emulsion formation. Three black dot indication of unstable emulsion. They are out of shaded nanoemulsion region because in these formulation oil was increase and Smix ration was decrease.

Selected nanoemulsion formulation

From above study NSS1, N1, NS1, NSE1, NSE2, NS2, NSE4, NS3, NS4 nanoemulsion shows better characteristics result which proved by above study so these nanoemulsion formulation was selected for further study.

Table No.2 Characterization of selected nanoemulsion.

Batch code	Smix Ratio	Ratio (O:S)	Percentage Transmittance (%)	Conductivity (mS/cm) **	Refractive index	Viscosity (Cp)	pH	Globule Size(nm)	Percent Drug Content
NSS1	1:1	1:9	98.61	0.172	1.361	128.13	5.45	172.9	98.36
N1	2:1	1:9	98.96	0.160	1.361	178.26	5.39	109.63	98.19
NS1	3:1	1:9	99.42	0.149	1.375	173.43	5.42	71.70	99.54
NSE1	3:1	1:8	99.09	0.157	1.362	122.90	5.38	103	98.00
NSE2	3:1	1:7	98.94	0.175	1.369	75.13	5.11	122	97.80
NS2	3:1	2:8	98.67	0.161	1.368	136.86	5.97	188.43	98.19
NSE4	3:1	2:7	98.43	0.183	1.375	106.80	5.39	191.30	98.25
NS3	3:1	3:7	97.75	0.184	1.390	97.66	5.37	197.36	98.04
NS4	3:1	4:6	96.42	0.211	1.392	76.3	5.12	226	98.02

All selected formulation given in Table No.2 of percentage transmittance this value decrease with increase the content of oil and decreases the transparency of formulation. So percent transmittance of selected formulation above 90% so all formulation have high clarity, transparency and also high percent transmittance less oil globule Size. Conductivity study indicated that all selected formulation was O/W type of nanoemulsion. Refractive index suppose of might have be in the range of 1.361-1.392. RI values increased with increase in concentration of oil and corresponding decrease in aqueous content. It was observed that the viscosity of all the formulations is ranges between 75.13-178cps. pH of selected formulation was found to be in the range of 5.11-5.97. Percent drug content study of selected formulation was found to be in the range of 97-99, which indicate that nanoemulsion have more drug loading efficiency and less chance of drug lost in during formulation. NS1 formulation show less droplet size (71.70 ± 3.06) than other formulation because it contain high concentration of surfactant and co-surfactant and NSS1 formulation show High droplet size (172.9 ± 6.60) than other formulation because it contain low concentration of surfactant and co-surfactant.

Polydispersity Index

Polydispersity Index analysis was performed on selected formulations by using Delsa nano Zeta Nanosizer. Polydispersity Index indicates the uniformity of droplet size with in formulation. The lower the polydispersity index, the higher the uniformity of the droplet size in the formulation. So NS1 formulation show polydispersity index is (0.256 ± 0.002) so which indicate the higher the uniformity of the droplet size within the formulation.

FT-IR Analysis of nanoemulsion formulation

Figure No.6 FT-IR spectra of NS1 formulation.

From this we could conclude that there were no physical and/or chemical interaction in between drug and excipient studied. The frequencies of functional groups of drug CBZ remained intact in physical mixture and formulation containing different excipients. So it was concluded that there was no major interaction occurred.

Droplet size distribution data of formulation

Figure No.7 Statistical droplet size distribution data of NS1 formulation.

NS1 CBZ nanoemulsion was selected as final formulation because it have less droplet size (71.70 ± 3.06) with lowers the polydispersity index (0.256 ± 0.002) than other formulation so which indicate the higher the uniformity of the droplet size within the formulation, less refractive index value (1.375 ± 0.0030) than other formulation that indicate it chemically stable and isotropic in nature and also high percent transmittance value that it indicate it high clarity than other formulation so it selected final formulation from all above formulation.

Zeta potential

Figure No.8 Statistical Zeta potential data of NS1 nanoemulsion formulation.

Zeta potential of NS1 formulation was given above Figure No.8. Zeta potential indicate stability of nanoemulsion. Zeta potential was charge on the droplet if zeta potential in negative range that indicate negative charge on droplet due negative charge on droplet these droplet not attract to each other so droplet does not mix to each other and produce long time stability of nanoemulsion. So NS1 formulation show -15.6 zeta potential value so it remain stable for long period time that less chance of droplet mixing and droplet size increment.

Transmission electron microscopy

Figure No.9 Transmission electron microscopically image of NS1 formulation at 50nm and 10 nm with droplet size measurement.

Morphology and structure of the nanoemulsion were studied using transmission electron microscopy and given in Figure No.9. NS1 formulation have less particle size than other formulation. Hence select for TEM study. TEM image of NS1 selected formulation clearly showing oil droplet with surrounding surfactant layer and also drug in the droplet of oil of nanoemulsion. Droplet Size measurement indicate that given droplet in the nano size and so we conclude that given NS1 formulation was nanoemulsion formulation.

Ex-vivo drug release Study

Ex-vivo drug release Study of Selected CBZ nanoemulsion formulation using sheep nasal mucosa as the nasal membrane which simulated with phosphate buffer pH-6

Figure No.10 Percent drug release of selected nanoemulsion formulation.

Percent drug release data given above Table No.8.54 According these Table No.8.54 decrease particle size so increase surface area so NS1 formulation shows high percent drug release in low time as compare to other formulation that indicate that decrease the droplet size increase percent drug release. Similarly NS4 less percent drug release as compare to other formulation that indicate increase the droplet size decrease percent drug release.

Tests for nasal cilio toxicity of selected nanoemulsion formulation.

Figure No.11 Histological photomicrograph of eosin-hematoxyline stained sheep nasal mucosa of treated with phosphate buffer pH-6.4 and isopropyl alcohol.

Figure No.12 Histological photomicrograph of eosin-hematoxyline stained sheep nasal mucosa of treated with NS1 nanoemulsion formulation.

Nasal cilio-toxicity studies were carried out in an attempt to evaluate any potential toxic effects of excipients used in the formulation on the nasal mucosa. The nasal mucosa P1 treated with phosphate Buffer (pH 6.4, negative control) showed no nasociliary damage (Figure No.11) and the nasal membrane remained intact, whereas the second nasal mucosa P2 treated with isopropyl alcohol which an extensive damage to nasal mucosa (Figure No.12) could be observed with positive control. However, the nasal mucosa P3 treated with NS1 CBZ nanoemulsion thus substantiating the safety of the excipients used in the formulation so excipient use in nanoemulsion formulation was safe for inhalation.

IN-VIVO CHARACTERIZATION

Anticonvulsant activity

Table No. 3 Anticonvulsant activity of CBZ nanoemulsion in rats.

Sr. No.	Body wt. (gm)	Treatment (Dose)	Time (sec) in various phases of convulsion				Recovery/ Death
			Flexion	Extensor	Clonus	Stupor	
1	208	Control	9	15	147	57	Recovery
2	207	Control	8	16	142	53	Recovery
3	206	Control	9	15	144	56	Recovery
Mean			8.66	15.33	142	53.33	
1	209	Standard	11	6	135	60	Recovery
2	205	Standard	14	7	151	62	Recovery
3	207	Standard	12	6	141	61	Recovery
Mean			12.33	6.33	142.33	61	
1	207	Test	7	4	152	41	Recovery
2	208	Test	12	5	154	44	Recovery
3	207	Test	11	6	152	43	Recovery
Mean			10	5	152.66	42.66	

The above Table No.3 showed the results of anticonvulsant property of drugs. It was observed that there is reduction in tonic extensor phase of rats treated with Phenytoin (Standard) and CBZ nanoemulsion(Test). Both phenytoin and CBZ showed reduction in tonic phase as compared to control; therefore we could say that the drug had anticonvulsant activity which was found out by maximal electro-shock-induced convulsions in rats.

In-vivo Study (Nasal absorption and brain distribution studies).

Figure No.13 Chromatograph of NS1 CBZ nanoemulsion formulation of rat brain and rat plasma extract after 60 min.

Table No.4 Concentration of CBZ in brain and plasma after intranasal administration of NS1 formulation in rats.

Sr.No.	Time (min)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	
		NS1 Formulation	
		Brain	Plasma
1	0	0	0
2	30	7.50 \pm 1.02	5.54 \pm 0.21
3	60	11.26 \pm 0.32	7.51 \pm 0.36
4	90	9.19 \pm 0.25	8.69 \pm 0.54
5	120	9.50 \pm 0.52	9.64 \pm 0.11
6	240	7.82 \pm 1.00	6.92 \pm 0.01
7	360	7.11 \pm 0.04	5.43 \pm 0.02
8	420	6.12 \pm 0.01	4.85 \pm 0.04

Figure No.14 Concentration of CBZ in brain after intranasal administration of NS1.

Figure No.15 Concentration of CBZ in plasma after intranasal administration of NS1.

Table No.5 Pharmacokinetic parameter of NS1 formulation upon intranasal administration in rats.

Sr.No.	Pharmacokinetic parameter	NS1 formulation	
		Brain	Plasma
1	C _{max} (µg/mL)	11.26±0.01	9.64±0.04
2	T _{max} (min)	60±5.05	120±3.84
3	AUC _{0-t} (µg/mL*min)	3312.9±1.05	2839.8±1.56
4	AUC _{0-inf} (µg/mL*min)	7805.16±1.00	5287.78±1.23
5	MRT (min)	750.04±15.13	534.97±16.23

The concentration of CBZ in brain and plasma was determined after intranasal administration of selected CBZ formulation NS1 (CBZ nanoemulsion) given above Table No.5 respectively and Figure No.8.49 and 8.50 of *in-vivo* study represents the mean brain tissue, and plasma concentration–time profiles of CBZ after intranasal administration of NS1 formulations to rats at a dose of 1 mg/kg. According above data we prove that drug pass through the Intranasal to brain because C_{max} (11.26±0.01 µg/mL) of NS1 CBZ nanoemulsion formulation in brain it was higher as compare to C_{max} (9.64±0.04 µg/mL) of within the Plasma with less T_{max} (60±5.05 min) value as compare to T_{max} (120±3.84 min) within plasma. So these indicate that drug directly pass in the via intranasal route through olfactory nerve and other pathway

CONCLUSION

The CBZ nanoemulsion (NS1) system containing 7.35% (v/v) Capmul MCM EP, 66.18% Tween-80: PEG-600 ratio (3:1) and 26.47% (v/v) water phase was found to be optimum for intranasal delivery of CBZ. That displayed an optical transparency of 99.42±0.81%, globule size of 71.70±3.06 nm, polydispersity index of 0.256±0.002 and zeta potential of -15.6±1.2. The formulation was found to be physically stable for 3 months at ambient conditions. *In-vitro* and *ex-vivo* permeation studies showed an initial burst of drug release at 30 min and CBZ nanoemulsion (NS1) show drug release upto 5 h. Hence drug release in sustained manner. C_{max} (12.47±0.21 µg/mL) of CBZ nanoemulsion was higher as compare oral formulation. From *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* data it can be concluded that the developed nanoemulsions formulation have great potential for intranasal to brain drug delivery. Enhanced rate and extent of transport of Ibuprofen following intranasal administration of MMEI may help in decreasing the dose and frequency of dosing and possibly maximize the therapeutic index. However, ratio of clinical benefits to the risk of the formulation developed in this investigation will decide its appropriateness in the clinical practice.

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